

Table S2. Primers for qRT-PCR

Gene	Primers for qRT-PCR
Linc00668-F	GGGTCCAAGGGATCTGCAAG
Linc00668-R	CCGCCCAAGATTCCTCTAGC
E-cadherin-F	GCTCTTCCAGGAACCTCTGTGATG
E-cadherin-R	AAGCGATGGCGGCATTGTAGG
N-cadherin-F	GCTCTTCCAGGAACCTCTGTGATG
N-cadherin-R	AAGCGATGGCGGCATTGTAGG
Vimentin-F	TTGCCGTTGAAGCTGCTAACTACC
Vimentin-R	AATCCTGCTCTCCTCGCCTTCC
Slug-F	TCAACAGCCAACAAATACCAAG
Slug-R	TTCTCCTTGGATTCTCGTAAG
GAPDH-F	CACCCACTCCTCCACCTTTG
GAPDH-R	CCACCACCCTGTTGCTGTAG
miR-147a RT primer	GTCGTATCCAGTGCAGGGTCCGAGGTATTCGCACTGGATACGACG CAGAA
miR-147a-F	CGCGGTGTGTGGAAATGC
miR-147a-R	AGTGCAGGGTCCGAGGTATT
U6 RT primer	GTCGTATCCAGTGCAGGGTCCGAGGTATTCGCACTGGATACGACA AAATA
U6-F	AGAGAAGATTAGCATGGCCCCTG
U6-R	ATCCAGTGCAGGGTCCGAGG